

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Online data analysis for biologists
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	21 August 2024
Time of event	1 - 4pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Galaxy is a web-based platform that lets you conduct accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biological research. Widely used by researchers world wide, Galaxy gives you access to 1000's of popular tools for analysis and processing of biological data. It is perfect for working with a wide range of big and small datasets including genome assembly, annotation, epigenetics, metabolomics, metagenomics, proteomics, statistics, transcriptomics, variant analysis and visualisation.</p> <p>This workshop provides an introduction to using Galaxy and available tools. Using an example dataset, you'll practice uploading data, choosing and running tools, and viewing the results. We'll share our top tips for managing your experiments and speeding up your analysis with workflows.</p> <p>The material covered in this workshop is freely available through the Galaxy Training Network.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom over two three and a half hour sessions.</p> <p>Dr Gareth led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants then completed code along exercises giving them a chance to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>In parallel to the live session, Zoom Chat was used to answer questions as they arose, troubleshoot and share tips and resources.</p> <p>The material covered in this workshop is freely available through the Galaxy Training Network.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule (included in this Zenodo record).</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p>

	Number of participants = 21
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/galaxy-intro-2024
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945 Galaxy
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This workshop is for Australian life science researchers and bioinformaticians. It is a beginners' workshop for people with no prior knowledge of Galaxy. It's suitable for researchers with data to analyse or bioinformaticians who will be providing support to Galaxy users. No programming experience is required.
Prerequisites	You must be associated with an Australian organisation for your application to be considered.
Technical requirements	Online Platform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zoom Participants required: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laptop with access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. Training infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The workshop made use of Galaxy Australia's Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS)
Learning outcomes	By the end of the workshop you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the key features of the Galaxy website: Tools, Histories and the Centre Panel Upload data into Galaxy from your computer or a public website Organise your data using tags Select and run tools Explore the results of your analysis Create a workflow that can be used to repeat your analysis Identify sources of support and further training
Lead Trainer	Dr Gareth Price, Galaxy Australia
Facilitators	Mike Thang, Galaxy Australia/ QCIF
Training material	Tutorial: https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/introduction/tutorials/galaxy-intro-101-everyone/tutorial.html

	<p>A recording of this workshop is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube Channel.</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PF39KjOvreM</p>
Related work	<p>This tutorial is part of the Galaxy Training Network:</p> <p>https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/</p>